

Work-life balance and Individual well-being of academicians in Nepal: The moderating role of Gender

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Abstract

Work-life balance is the central concern of everyday discourses due to ever changing working environment and high work demands. Balancing one's career with personal life is challenging that affects people's satisfaction level and wellness. The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of work-life balance towards the individual well-being of academicians. It also aimed to examine the moderating effect of gender on the relationship between work-life balance and individual well-being.

The sample included 400 academicians from 22 different colleges in Kathmandu valley running as constituent and affiliated by four universities. The study employed correlation and regression analysis for analyzing data. Correlation analysis indicated the statistically significant relationship among the study variables. However, study revealed no significant relationship between personal life spillover on work and life satisfaction. The study found work-life balance as significant predictor of individual well-being. Results revealed significant effect of dimensions of work-life balance towards life satisfaction and psychological health. The study resulted no moderating effect of gender on relationship between work-life balance and well-being. Most of the study results are consistent with past studies. The results have several practical implications highlighted in the study.

Keywords: Work-life balance, academician, well-being, life satisfaction, psychological health

Introduction

Integration of personal life and work life has become the challenge due to changing patterns of lifestyles, changing pattern of work, social changes and competition for growth. Work-life balance is a central concern of everyday discourses (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011; Greenhaus, Collins, & Shaw, 2003; Haar, Russo, Sune, & Mallaterre, 2013) ^[11, 10, 13] as it plays the vital role for well-being of individual and sound operation of an organization (e.g., Kluczyk, 2013; Burdzinska & Rutowska, 2015; Singh & Amanjot, 2013) ^[16, 5, 25]. One's livelihood is earned through the work, therefore, it has significant influence on quality of life. At present, the organizations are facing heightened competition due to wave of globalization and changes in general environmental factors that put pressures on employees to increase performance, to use extra effort and the long working hours (Morin, 2004 as cited in Burdzinska & Rutowska, 2015; Sheppard, 2016) ^[5, 24]. The major issue under work life balance is to combine paid work with the individual's household work such as to take care of young

infants, elder generation, household chores including activities such as study, exercise, community work, hobbies, etc. The individual struggles to carry out such high work demand roles and household chores which usually create a state of conflict and resource competition as we possess limited resources such as time and human energy (Lu & Kao, 2013) ^[17]. Employees need adequate rest after exertion of efforts at work to recover and recharge both physically and psychologically. In these scenarios, balancing one's career with a personal and family life is challenging that impact on a person's satisfaction both in their work and in personal life's role (Broers, 2005 as cited in Mukhtar, 2012) ^[20].

Academic sector is becoming comparatively more stressful with the potential serious consequences for the faculty and the quality of higher education (Kinman & Jones, 2008) ^[15]. The reforms in university education system such as implementation of a stringent assessment system, semester education system, accompanying research opportunities, the culture shifting, financial pressures, structural and

managerial diversity (Noor, 2011) [22], made the teaching learning activities more complex and challenging. They need to carry out an academic research and publication demand for promotion and tenure as well as need to be updated for effective teaching learning activists. They are feeling overburdened due to their academic workload and career issues (Hakenen, Bakker, & Schaufeli, 2006) [14]. Similarly, the survey conducted on work life balance in 2018 in academic sectors also resulted that academics are feeling more stressed, underpaid, and struggling to fit time for personal relationships and family around their ever-growing workloads (Bothwell, 2018) [4]. Thus, due to the increasing job demands, work-life balance of academicians seems poor and perceived a greater discrepancy between their real and ideal levels of work integration.

The changing role of academicians demands high resources that raise high levels of conflict between work life and home life which was the strongest predictor of psychological distress (Rana & Panchal, 2014) [23]. In addition, They haven't only reported the psychologically distressed due to higher levels of job demands, but were also less satisfied with jobs and more likely to have seriously considered career options outside academia (Kinman & Jones, 2008) [15]. Academicians are facing a lot of daily struggle to maintain work life balance and satisfaction (Malik & Allam, 2021) [18]. Thus, this scenario leads the necessity to study work-life balance and its effect on well-being of academicians.

Understanding the nature, antecedent and consequences of work-life balance and occupational attitudes are widely studied in management literatures that are the precursors of employees' performance; however, those issues have rarely addressed and studied in the Nepalese organization (Bajracharya *et al.*, n.d; Tamang, 2008) [27]. Most of the Nepalese University teachers are being engaged in one or more institutions because of the resource constraints such as financial, physical and technical (Bajracharya *et al.*, n.d). They are having multiple roles and responsibilities towards different parties as elsewhere that force them for giving excess time and effort. Hence, this study focuses on identifying the condition of work-life balance and its consequent effect on individual well-being of Nepalese academicians.

Review of Literature

The integration of conflict approach and spillover approach explaining the relationship between work and non-work aspects has been considered for the purpose of this study that incorporates work spillover in personal life (WSPL) and personal life spillover in work (PLSW). The spillover approach emphasized both positive and negative reciprocal effects on each other of work and non-work domains (Guest 2002) [12]. Work life balance enhancers (WLBE) is used as the positive aspect of work-life issues in this study which focus on spreading satisfaction and stimulation at work to higher levels of energy and satisfaction at home, whereas negative spillover arises problems and conflict at work drain and preoccupies the individual that make unable to equally participate in personal life role. Work-life balance is define as subjective evaluation, which can be understood in terms of how satisfied an individual is with his or her functioning in both work roles and non-work roles along with the values

places by individuals in the process (Guest, 2002; Wilkinson, 2013) [12, 28]. Work-life balance is a state of balance, an individual attempt to maintain in his/her working life and his personal life. It is about people having a control over when, how and where to work.

Work-life balance is significant precursors of an individual's psychological well-being, work productivity and overall sense of harmony in life (Clark, 2000) [7]. Authors (e.g. Burdzinska & Rutowska, 2015; Singh, 2014; Singh & Amanjot, 2013) [5, 25] have also agreed that work life balance is a significant determinant of well-being of individual people. Another study conducted by Haar *et al.* (2013) [13] in seven different cultural contexts emphasizes the crucial role that work-life balance plays in promoting greater job satisfaction, life satisfaction and mental health. The study has found strong support for work-life balance being beneficial for employees from various cultures in which culture moderates the relationship as well. Similarly, Sheppard (2016) [24] has also concluded that work-life balance programs could help improve organizational culture and overall employee performance as it provides satisfaction and good functioning in both the workplace and personal life. Well-being is a crucial component of a happy and good quality of life (Diener, 2000) [8], which is associated with happiness, satisfaction, optimism, vitality, passion, and self-actualization. Life satisfaction is a conscious, cognitive and global judgements of one's own life ranging from negative to positive (Diener, 2000; Singh & Amanjot, 2013) [8, 25]. Psychological health also refers as having a sense of happiness or lacking of psychological distress (Wilkinson, 2013) [28]. Psychologically healthy people tend to be capable of thinking clearly, developing socially, and learning new skills and updated with the present state.

Achieving a good balance between work life and personal life is a growing concern for the professional people for having a quality life. Though, this issue has begun, especially through working women, maintaining balance is the major challenges for both men and women due to changes in patterns of work and traditionally set gender role stereotypes at present. The changing workforce and the increase in dual-earning families had a dramatic effect on the role of men as well (Wilkinson, 2013) [28]. The previous study had revealed that male faculty members have a lot of responsibility in the universities than the female faculty members (Malik & Allam, 2021) [18]. In this context, it is necessary to understand the existing relationship of work life balance and well-being from the perspectives of both men and women.

Most of the studies regarding work and family issues have been dominated by conflict approach (Adhikary, 2016) [1] and found negative consequences such as low satisfaction, absenteeism, low level of organizational commitment, high turnover and low motivation (Tamang, 2008) [27]. However, several researchers have look this issue from enrichment perspective and argued that participating different roles expand their energy and the experience gain in one field will likely to support to play roles in another field (e.g. Burdzinska & Rutowska, 2015; Chhetri, 2014) [5, 6]. This study has incorporated both the work family enrichment and conflict perspective as suggested by Chhetri (2014) [6] to see how both the constructs are perceived in the organizational context of Nepal and will be concerned with identifying the

positive outcome of work-life balance on employees' well-being.

Individual well-being including psychological health of academicians is a crucial elements for effective educational activities in universities. However at present, academic sector is becoming comparatively more stressful with the potential serious consequences for the faculty and the quality of higher education (Kinman & Jones, 2008) [15]. They are feeling overburdened due to their academic workload and career issues (Hakenen, Bakker, & Schaufeli, 2006) [14]. The changing role of academicians demands high resources that raise high level of conflict between work life and home life which was the strongest predictor of psychological distress (Rana & Panchal, 2014) [23]. In addition, They haven't only reported the psychologically

distressed due to higher levels of job demands, but were also less satisfied with jobs and more likely to have seriously considered career options outside academia (Kinman & Jones, 2008) [15]. Thus, due to the increasing job demands, work-life balance of academicians seems poor and perceived a greater discrepancy between their real and ideal levels of work integration. Therefore, this study seeks to fill the gap by examining both perspectives of work-life balance and its consequent effect on well-being of academicians in Nepalese context. The study also purposed to consider the Gender differences and examine its moderating effect in the relationship between Work-Life balance and well-being of academicians. The theoretical framework for this study purpose is shown in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Research Framework

Research Hypotheses

- H₁:** There is a significant positive relationship between work-life balance and individual well-being.
- H_{2a}:** Work Spillover in Personal Life has a significant negative relationship with Life satisfaction.
- H_{2b}:** Work Spillover in Personal Life has a significant negative relationship with psychological health.
- H_{3a}:** Personal life Spillover in work has a significant negative relationship with Life satisfaction.
- H_{3b}:** Personal life Spillover in work has a significant negative relationship with psychological health.
- H_{4a}:** Work life balance enhancer has a significant positive relationship with Life satisfaction.
- H_{4b}:** Work life balance enhancer has a significant positive relationship with psychological health.
- H₅:** The relationship between work-life balance and individual well-being is moderated by gender.

Research Methodology

This study followed positivist epistemology and quantitative approach to investigate the relationship between study variables. Descriptive and analytical research design has been used in this study. The population for this study comprises both part-time and full-time faculties of different colleges, which are affiliated under different universities in Kathmandu Valley. In this study, two-stage sampling is made, initially, the colleges operating as constituent and affiliated with four universities, namely, Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu University, Pokhara University and Purbanchal University were chosen randomly as sampling unit. As per the researcher's convenience, the colleges were selected. Then the faculties who teach Bachelor and above degree, responsible to supervise the research project were

considered in the sample of the study. The convenient sampling was employed to collect the responses from accessible group of respondents. Cross-sectional and self-administered questionnaire technique was used to collect responses from the participants. Six hundred fifty questionnaires were distributed with the expectation of getting a minimum of 384 responses. Out of total questionnaires, 460 responses were collected with a response rate of 76.67 percent. Among them 400 were found usable, valid and usable for data analysis. The SPSS software was used to clean the data, process and analyze the data. For robustness test, hierarchical regressions were employed to test the hypotheses where demographic information including university, gender, age, qualification, level of employment marital status, status of employment and years of experience were considered as a control variables. Moderation effect of gender on the relationship between work life balance and well-being was carried out by using Moderated Multiple Regression (MMR). Control variables were used to control the effect of demographic variables on study variables. Consent and data privacy were maintained.

Results

Out of 400 respondents, the number of male respondents was 297 and 103 female respondents (25.8%) as shown in Table 1. Similarly, 79.8% were married and rest 20.3% unmarried. In terms of age almost more than half were from the age group of 31-40. The majority of the respondents (76.8%) have completed master degree. The majority (65.8%) respondents were working as an assistant professor and others are professors, associate professor and others. The majority 60% was full-timers and rest 40% part-timer.

Table 1: Respondents Characteristics (N = 400)

Variables	Categories	No. of Respondents	Percent
Gender	male	297	74.3
	Female	103	25.8
Marital Status	Married	319	79.8
	Unmarried	81	20.3
Age	Under 30	81	20.3
	31 - 40	209	52.3
	41 – 50	81	20.3
	51 – 60	20	5
	Over 60	9	2.3
Qualification	Bachelor	11	2.8
	Master	307	76.8
	M.Phil.	67	16.8
	Ph.D.	15	3.8
Level of Employment	Professor	12	3
	Associate professor	21	5.3
	Assistant professor	263	65.8
	Other faculties	104	26.6
Status	Full-time	240	60
	Part-time	160	40
Years of Experience	1 to 5	134	33.5
	6 to 10	128	32
	11 to 15	61	15.3
	16 to 20	54	13.5
	over 20	23	5.8

Note: Developed by the authors using data from questionnaire survey.

Reliability and correlation analysis

To determine the reliability, Cronbach alphas was calculated for each instrument, i.e., work spillover in personal life, Personal life spillover in work, work life balance enhancers, life satisfaction and Psychological distress. The reliability analysis result are presented in Table 2. According to

Mukhtar (2012) ^[20] coefficient of less than 0.6 indicates marginal to low internal consistency hence, all the dimensions are considered acceptable for further analysis. Each dimension has shown the acceptable Cronbach’s alpha, ranging from $\alpha = .680$ to $\alpha = .85$.

Table 2: Mean, S.D., Cronbach Alpha, and Correlations Analysis for Different Instruments

Dimensions	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's alpha	WSPL	PLSW	WLBE	LS	PD	WLB	Well-being
Work spillover on Personal Life	3.09	0.64	0.85	1						
Personal life spillover on work	2.61	0.79	0.79	0.521**	1					
Work-life balance Enhancers	3.43	0.8	0.68	0.6	0.048	1				
Life satisfaction	3.32	0.68	0.73	-0.122*	-0.058	0.188**	1			
Psychological distress	1.76	0.46	0.8	0.202**	.340**	-0.207**	-0.235**	1		
Work-life balance				0.929	.743**	.273**	.235**	-.224**	1	
Well-being				.119*	.289**	-0.082	.381**	.809**	.171**	1

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Source: Developed by the author using data from questionnaire survey.

The mean value of WSPL indicates that Nepalese academicians perceived moderate to high level of interference from work to their personal life roles. Similarly, the average value of PLSW shows that they perceived low level of Personal life spillover in work. This result indicates that Nepalese academicians felt low interference from personal roles to their work life roles. The mean value of work-life enhancers indicates relatively higher sense of enhancement from their work to life roles and life roles to work. Similarly, the mean value of Life satisfaction indicates that they seem quite happy with their present status of life. However, scores on the psychological distress lower than average indicates that academicians felt less psychological disorder and distress, which indicated that academicians tend to be psychologically well.

The correlations in the Table 2 indicate that the relationships

among work spillover on personal life, personal life spillover in work, work-life balance enhancers, life satisfaction and psychological distress and overall score of work-life balance and well-being are statistically significant ($p < .01$) and the nature of the relationships are positive and are in the expected directions which depicts that employees who are able to maintain work-life balance tend to have quality of life and satisfied with their job. Work Spillover on Personal Life had statistically significant negative relationship with life satisfaction and statistically significant positive relationship with Psychological distress, which shows negatively related with psychological health. Similarly, Personal Life Spillover on Work had statistically significant positive relationship with psychological distress, which indicates negative effect on psychological health. Furthermore, Work-life balance enhancers had statistically

significant negative relationship with psychological distress, inversely positive relationship with psychological health and statistically significant positive relationship with life satisfaction. The result also shows that the overall score of work-life balance had statistically significant positive correlation with overall score of well-being. Though, personal life spillover on work was negatively related to life satisfaction, it is statistically not significant. Thus, hypothesis 3a could not be supported.

Regression Analysis of Work-life balance and well-being

For the robustness in the relationship between proposed hypotheses, regression equation was used for further investigation. For analysis, at first the control variables (gender, marital status, age, qualification, level of employment, status and years of experience) were introduced then independent variables were introduced in second step. Table 3 shows the model is fit as statistically significant (F = 9.265, $p < 0.001$) results along with coefficient value of well-being which was statistically significant ($\beta = .135, p < 0.01$). It indicates that work-life balance has significant influence on achieving individual well-being. The demographic variables such as marital status, level of employment and status were found to be statistically significant in this model.

Table 3: Effect of Work-life balance on individual well-being

	Well-being	
	Step 1 β	Step 2 β
Gender	-0.017	-0.019
Marital Status	.302***	.298***
Age	.053*	.056*
Qualification	-0.018	-0.023
Level of Employment	.165***	.149***
Status	.103*	.099*
Years of Experience	0.075	0.071
Work-life balance		.135**
ΔR^2	0.141	0.018
F	9.226***	9.265***
R ²		0.159

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Source: Developed by the author using data from questionnaire survey

Regression Analysis of Work spillover on Personal life to Life satisfaction and Psychological Health

The regression result of life satisfaction (Table 4) shows that the regression model is statistically significant (F = 2.078, $p < 0.05$). It also shows that work spillover personal life was statistically significant ($\beta = -.133, p < 0.01$) which indicates that it has significant influence on achieving happy life. However, no any demographic variables were significant in this model. Similarly, Psychological distress was regressed on independent variable WSPL. The regression result (Table 4) shows that the regression model is statistically significant (F = 14.253, $p < 0.001$), and shows work spillover on personal life was statistically significant ($\beta = .191, p < 0.001$) which indicates that it has significant influence on psychological well-being of people. Only the demographic variables such as marital status, age and level of employment were found to be statistically significant in this model. Work spillover on personal life has positive and significant influence on psychological distress. Inversely, it

has significant negative relationship with psychological health. Thus, it supports the hypothesis 2a and hypothesis 2b.

Table 4: The regression of WSPL on Life satisfaction and Psychological health

	Life Satisfaction		Psychological distress	
	Step 1 β	Step 2 β	Step 1 β	Step 2 β
Gender	0.039	0.044	-0.047	-0.053
Marital Status	-0.1	-0.101	.382***	.383***
Age	-0.014	-0.003	.116*	.112*
Qualification	-0.011	-0.007	-0.006	-0.016
Level of Employment	0.081	0.097	.122*	0.100*
Status	0.056	0.055	0.066	0.067
Work Spillover on personal life		-0.133**		.191***
ΔR^2	0.018	0.017	0.167	0.036
F	1.231	2.078**	13.133***	14.253***
R ²		0.036		0.203

Source: Developed by the author using data from questionnaire survey.

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; Psychological health is measured through the level of Psychological distress.

Regression analysis of personal life spillover to work on life satisfaction and psychological health

The regression result (Table 5) shows that the regression model is not statistically significant which indicates personal spillover on work had negative insignificant relationship with life satisfaction. Thus hypothesis 3a was not supported. Similarly, regression effect of PLSW on psychological health shows that the regression model is statistically significant (F = 17.143, $p < 0.001$), which indicates that it has significant influence on psychological well-being of people. The demographic variables such as marital status and age were found to be statistically significant in this model. PLSW positive and significant influence on psychological distress, which indicates the significant negative relationship with Psychological health. Thus, it support hypothesis 3b.

Table 5: The regression of PLSW on Life satisfaction and psychological health

	Life Satisfaction		Psychological distress	
	Step 1 β	Step 2 β	Step 1 β	Step 2 β
Gender	0.039	0.038	-0.047	-0.041
Marital Status	-0.1	-0.091	.382***	.343***
Age	-0.014	-0.016	.116*	.124*
Qualification	-0.011	-0.007	-0.006	-0.019
Level of Employment	0.081	0.091	.122*	0.082
Status	0.056	0.05	0.066	0.058
Personal Spillover on work		-1.226		.268***
ΔR^2	0.018	0.004	0.167	0.067
F	1.231	0.263	13.133***	17.143***
R ²		0.022		0.234

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; Psychological health is measured through the level of psychological distress.

Source: Developed by the author using data from questionnaire survey.

Regression analysis of work life enhancers on life satisfaction and psychological health

The regression result (Table 6) shows that the regression

model is statistically significant ($F = 3.025, p < 0.01$), which indicates that work life enhancers has significant influence on achieving happy life. However, no any demographic variables were significant in this model.

Table 6: The regression of work life enhancers on Life satisfaction and Psychological health

	Life Satisfaction		Psychological distress	
	Step 1 β	Step 2 β	Step 1 β	Step 2 β
Gender	0.039	0.038	-0.047	-0.041
Marital Status	-0.1	-0.091	.382***	.343***
Age	-0.014	-0.016	.116*	.124*
Qualification	-0.011	-0.007	-0.006	-0.019
Level of Employment	0.081	0.091	.122*	0.082
Status	0.056	0.05	0.066	0.058
Personal Spillover on work		-1.226		.268***
ΔR^2	0.018	0.004	0.167	0.067
F	1.231	0.263	13.133***	17.143***
R ²		0.022		0.234

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$; Psychological health is measured through the level of psychological distress.

Source: Developed by the author using data from questionnaire survey.

Similarly, Psychological distress was regressed on independent variable WLBE controlling demographic variables such as gender, marital status, age, qualification, level of employment and status. The regression result (Table 6) shows that the regression model is statistically significant ($F = 14.253, p < 0.001$), which indicates significant influence on psychological well-being of people. The demographic variables such as marital status, age and level of employment were found to be statistically significant in this model. Work-Life Balance enhancers has positive significant influence on life satisfaction and negative influence on psychological distress inversely, positive relationship with psychological health. Thus, it support hypothesis H4a and H4b.

Multiple moderated Regression analysis

For moderating analysis a new variable was created through interaction of independent variable and moderating variable i.e. (independent \times moderating variable) in the beginning. Hierarchical regression was done by entering variables in three steps.

Table 7: Multiple moderated Regression analysis of Gender on WLB and Well-being

	Step 1 β	Step 2 β	Step 3 β
Marital Status	.302***	.298***	.300***
Age	.53	0.056	0.055
Qualification	-0.016	-0.023	-0.024
Level of Employment	.166***	.149**	.152**
Status	.103*	.099*	.098*
Years of Experience	.76	0.071	0.073
Work-life Balance		139**	0.064
Gender		-0.019	-0.153
WLB \times Gender			0.155
ΔR^2	0.141	0.018	0.001
F	10.766***	9.265***	8.252***
R ²		0.159	0.16

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Source: Developed by the author using data from questionnaire survey.

The Multiple moderated Regression analysis result (Table 7) shows that the regression MMR model is statistically significant ($F = 8.252, p < 0.001$). However, the result shows that beta coefficient of interacting variable was not statistically significant. Therefore, the moderating effect of gender could not be established in the relationship between work-life balance and well-being. Thus, Hypothesis H5 was not accepted.

Summary of Hypotheses Testing Results

Based on the correlation and regression analysis results eight hypothesis along with one moderation relationship were examined. Among them six direct hypothesis were supported but two others hypothesis failed to support as shown in Table 8

Table 8: Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Hypothesized Relationship	Findings
H1	WLB	Well-being	Positive	Supported
H2a	WSPL	LS	Negative	Supported
H2b	WSPL	PH	Negative	Supported
H3a	PLSW	LS	Negative	Not Supported
H3b	PLSW	PH	Negative	Supported
H4a	WLBE	LS	Positive	Supported
H4b	WLBE	PH	Positive	Supported
H5	WLB	Well-being	Moderation (Gender)	Not Supported

Discussion

This study aimed to analyze the effect of work-life balance on individual well-being as well as identifying the moderating effect of gender on the proposed relationship. Out of the 8 hypotheses, 2 were rejected with no moderating effect of gender and rest all hypotheses were accepted. This study reveals that work-life balance is the significant predictor of individual well-being. This finding is consistent with the findings of the previous researchers (e.g. Haar *et al.*, 2013; Burdzinska & Rutowska, 2015; Singh & Amanjyot, 2013; Sheppard, 2016) [13, 5, 24]. Hence, the people who could maintain the balance between the work life and his personal life could achieve happy and satisfied life and can have an effective psychological functioning.

The findings suggest that there is no differences between male and female academicians on perceiving work spillover in personal life, Personal life spillover in work, work life balance enhances, life satisfaction and psychological health. This result is consistent with the findings of previous researchers (e.g. Gorsy & Panwar, 2016; Nayeem & Tripathy, 2012) [9, 21]. Both male and female experience a struggle to maintain work-life balance and well-being. However, this findings is not consistent and contradict with the findings of previous studies (Wilkinson, 2013; Chhetri, 2014) [28, 6].

The study reveals that the more Work Spillover in Personal life is experienced by individuals the less satisfied they are with their present state of life which is aligns with the findings of previous researches (e.g. Moreno-Jimenez *et al.*, 2008; Tamang, 2008; Singh & Amanjyot, 2013) [19, 27]. Similarly, the finding shows that the more work interference with personal life is experienced by individuals the more

psychological distress they felt which is consistent with Moreno-Jimenez *et al.*, (2008) ^[19]. The high job demands resulted higher level of distress, lower concentration power, sleep awareness, lack of self-confidence hence, poor psychological functioning.

The study found no relationship of PLSW and Life satisfaction as expected which is similar to the study reported by Kluczyk (2013) ^[16]. Apart from this, Moreno-Jimenez *et al.*, (2008) ^[19] found that when people have to attend family demands, their performance at work can be reduced, descent on work which diminish the level of life satisfaction as well. The finding reveals that personal chores interfere with work resulted the psychological distress as PLSW is negatively related to psychological health. This finding is consistent with Moreno-Jimenez *et al.*, (2008) ^[19]. The study found the significant positive relationship between work life enhancers and Life satisfaction as it was expected which is consistent with previous studies (Amin & Malik, 2017; Chhetri, 2014; Greenhaus & Powell, 2006 as cited in Burdzinska & Rutowska, 2015) ^[18, 6, 5]. The finding reveals that the facilitation and support from both family and work domains enhance the work life balance and hence reduce the psychological distress indicating psychologically healthy. The previous literature also show the consistent finding regarding work life enhancers and well being (Burdzinska & Rutowska, 2015; Haar *et al.*, 2013; Wilkinson, 2013) ^[5, 13, 28].

Practical and Research Implications

This research found that work-life balance has a significant positive influence on the well-being of academicians. The study results suggest that academic institutes have to pay more attention for creating a flexible working environment that facilitates for maintaining work-life balance as it enhances the well-being of employees. Human resource professional should focus on developing different HR policy and practices in such a way that leads to have work-life balance. Future research could be extended to different other professionals with different work characteristics and troubling to balance the roles such as shift work professional and health service sector. Similarly, different demographic variables such as spouse's employment status, parents with children, religion, caste, areas beyond Kathmandu Valley etc. could be extended for studying work-life balance in Nepalese context.

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